

CONNECTING EMOTION TO PRODUCT CUSTOMIZATION AN INTEGRATION MODEL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The act of seating is a good way of understanding the needs of user-centered design in connection to the final product. Several studies have explored the relation between pressure levels and the perceived comfort, or discomfort, of people in their relation with the seat (Schifferstein e Hekkert 2008).

People with pressure ulcer problems usually do not have the opportunity to communicate with specialized technicians to obtain products that improve their quality of life. For this reason it is important to have integrated communication tools that permit the communication between people and technologies.

This work aims to contribute towards an improvement of the well being of users with special needs, through the prevention of pressure ulcers. Based on collecting and communicating user information in an integrated system, that uses communication between the user and specialized technicians, to develop customized products supported by rapid fabrication technologies.

Keywords: emotional design, design methodology, rapid prototyping, user centered design, customization.

INTRODUCTION

Recent studies on the evolution of the design concept show a trend towards the design more focused in the man as user, particularly in respect to the pleasure relation that the product permits, based on its interaction with the product (Zhang and Dong, 2009; Fuad-Luke 2005).

In terms of user centered design (UCD) methodologies, there is a wide range of processes where the final user is involved during the design process. Sometimes participating or influencing the process development, with contribution in the perception of its needs through inquiries or usability tests, in others as a participant member of the actual product/system development (Abrás, 2004).

In fact, what has been addressed, with varying degrees of user participation, is the relation the user has with the product. Desmett (2007) in Product Experience focus mechanisms to evaluate the user experience with the product and uses a set of emotional tools that are usually associated to the psychophysical analysis with reference to discomfort.

THE USER: PEOPLE WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

In an approach to user centered design, People with Special Needs (PSN) are users that due to having specific particularities must be considered during the design process. In this particular case, more than being a source of observation or object of inquiries/tests they are a dynamic source of information that must be considered in the design process in order to develop objects that can solve their specific needs.

Within the definition of people with special needs (PSN) are people that, either consciously or unconsciously, have limitations of their motor skills. These limitations can be due to physical impairments or due to post-surgical situations. In the case of people that have physical impairments, or limited motor abilities, that limitation is conscious, but in the case of patients that in situations of post-surgical anesthesia loose sensibility, that limitation is

unconscious. In both cases these persons lack the capacity for autonomous movements (Providência et al., 2011).

According to Reddy et al. (2006), the majority of PSN suffer from problems related to the contact of certain body areas with support surfaces. Caused by the lack of motor autonomy, these areas are subjected to excessive skin pressure, which restricts blood flow, leading to the emergence of pressure ulcers (PU).

PU result of increased external pressure and are usually located over bony prominences. These are cutaneous wounds of ischemic origin that can vary in intensity, being superficial or deep (Blanes et al., 2004).

PU and PU treatment affect tremendously patients quality of life, not only because they cause discomfort and pain, but also because they interfere in the personal and social life of the individuals and in their psychological well-being (Gorecki et al., 2009). According to Reddy et al. (2006), the economical impact of PU treatment is highly significant, and thus justifies preventive approaches extremely focused in target groups, since, in their opinion, this will certainly be less expensive than the PU treatment.

According to K. Vanderwee et al. (2008), effective measures for preventing PU are those that aim to reduce the intensity and/or duration of pressure and shear forces. One of the most common preventive practices is to reduce the pressure duration by alternating the area under pressure, through patient repositioning every 2 hours, or every 4 hours if using appropriated support surfaces to redistribute pressure (Krapfl and Gray, 2008). Specialized support surfaces are mattresses or cushions, which reduce or alleviate the pressure that the patient weight exerts on the skin and subcutaneous tissues as they are compressed against the bed or seat surface (Reddy et al., 2006).

EMOTIONAL/PYCHOPHYSIC DATA FOR USER INTERPRETATION

Normally when we feel well, we can show a smile or express that feeling more unconsciously in some other form, but in reality it is difficult to measure these parameters. Comfort is more related to the emotional

issues, being a more intangible area, while discomfort approaches more pragmatic issues such as physical aspects (Vink, 2008).

In this sense, science used the discomfort analysis not just because it is more perceptive, but also because of the easiness in creating mechanisms to “measure” the discomfort and because those mechanisms can be readily used to create assessment grades. The issues related to discomfort, as noted previously, are widely used to understand the user relation with the objects, sometimes using inquiries, tests or through the observation of user’s expressive behaviors such as facial expressions.

In this area the approach is made through the use of psychophysical tools to support the development of products that permit improving users quality of life, both at the psychophysical as at the emotional level. The psychophysical tools addressed in the present work are focused in four specific areas:

- Body pressure and the duration of the pressure – through its registration in pressure maps, making it possible the assessment of one of the causes of PUs.
- The movement – through the perception of the relation between body and pressure, and also by relating these with specific time frames.
- Facial expressions – through assessing the non-verbal emotional relation of the user to certain stimuli.
- Mood scales – through assessing, in the same way as facial expressions, the emotion response to certain stimuli, such as seating for long periods of time.

Pressure data acquisition systems usually collect quantitative information, based on user interaction with the surface, thus allowing a rapid read of the pressure area. The pressure area is shown as numerical values expressed in mmHg, or in two or three dimension graphics (Figure 1).

Such is the case of the F-Scan systems (Tekscan Official Web) of the Tekscan company. These systems allow the mapping and monitoring of for example: foot pressure on the insole of the shoe, or

Figure 1. 2D and 3D map obtained from pressure acquisition system.

the case of the pressure forces exerted on a bicycle seat during the cycling activity (Wilson and Bush 2007) where the crossing of the pressure data with the movement capture throughout the pedal cycle allows data crossing in a more complete study.

In the present work the system used for pressure data acquisition was the Tekscan. Tekscan is a tool based on a film with pressure sensors that allows the mapping of pressures in a given area. This technology allows data acquisition by different set of frames over time.

MOCAP is a motion capture system consisting of a set of optical devices, magnetic or others, that based on a set of marks, sensors, built in strategic points such as the user's joints, registers the movements he performs. In the optical case, the cameras arranged surrounding the user collect movement data, using a system of retro reflective markers (Wilson and Bush, 2007). The movements collected by the system allow detecting location, posture and time frame to be sent to a server where these data can be crossed with data from other technology sources, as for example a flexible pressure sensor matrix (Andreoni et al., 2002).

Facial expressions belong to the set of physical means of human non-verbal emotional communication (Verissimo, 2000). Already in 1872 DARWIN recognized the analysis of facial expressions as a valid way of analyzing the communication of emotional states (Verissimo, 2000). During the last

half of the XX-th century several researchers have shown that there is a group of emotions that have characteristic non-verbal expressions that are recognized in the same way in different cultures, namely the expressions associated to anger, contempt, disgust, happiness, fear, sadness and surprise (Tracy et al., 2009). Based in this group of emotions different facial expressions evaluation systems have been developed to support the objective evaluation of non-verbal emotional behavior. Currently one of the methods more widely used is the Ekman and Friesen's method, the Facial Action Coding System (FACS). This method is based on a system of Pictures of Facial Affect that constitutes a database for use in behavioral research (Tracy et al., 2009).

For Almeida (2010), the emotional analysis based on the facial expressions, when applied in the study of the emotional relations at the visceral level of design, should be seen as an asset to product design.

The Borg scale is a scale that allows evaluating the emotional response in face of certain stimuli. The Borg CR10 scale is a subjective scale, representing a part of the Borg scale, which from a set of questions extracts information's regarding personal comfort/discomfort characteristics. The scale is based on an inquiry methodology where, over a period of time, questions are posed to the user in order to evaluate its degree of discomfort.

The scale ranges from 0.5 to 10. It allows the use of decimal values, and in special cases if necessary values superior or inferior to 10 or 0.5 respectively can also be used. From the moment the user starts the test he is instructed to report periodically on his degree of satisfaction/relation with the effort until a maximum value is achieved. One way to validate these results is by crossing the values obtained with the Borg scale with the evaluation of mood changes through the analysis of facial expressions. Facial expressions evaluation, as well as other similar techniques, allows interpretation of the user reaction to a set of stimuli in a more or less tangible way, either based on quantitative or qualitative evaluations.

Vink (2008), about the comfort/discomfort relationship with the product, refers that each user has his own opinion and thus designing a product that is comfortable for each user is complicated. Vink in his work uses a mood scale, similar to the Borg scale, named "localized discomfort posture", to assess the discomfort relation in specific body areas. In this case, after the user has understood the scale, the user is subjected to a test where he has to lift a 5 Kg weight with the arms at a 90° position. This allows correlating the localized postural discomfort with the subjective evaluation that is simultaneously made using inquiries (Vink, 2008).

From the user comfort relation with the seat interface, Shen and Parson (1997) reported that the main tool for assessing the discomfort is based on the measurement of pressure forces and their distribution over the area occupied by the user, combined with the duration of the time period resting in the seating position that will lead to discomfort due to compression.

Based on this principle, one may formulate two specifications to be considered during the design process: the uniform pressure distribution and the shape of the seat base. The lack of references in this area lead us to consider that this problem has not been entirely solved and therefore there is a need to find new solutions through crossing the previously referred emotional/psychophysical evaluation systems as methodology in a design approach, hitherto referred to in this way.

Alongside, the rapid manufacturing and customization technologies emerge as technologies that might come to solve the relationship with the particular user.

INTEGRATED MODEL

According to Putnik (2005, pg 20), "The information systems built on the information field paradigm do not produce sterile data, but aim to generate and communicate information that can lead to true knowledge that helps people to perceive, understand, value, and act in the world".

People with pressure ulcer problems usually do not have the opportunity to communicate with specialized technicians to obtain products that, based in the most recent technologies, improve their quality of life. For this reason it is important to develop integrated communication tools that permit the communication between people and technologies.

In this work, having started from user centered design methods we developed a system built between the user emotional/psychophysical data and the communication with the technical experts, allowing the synchronization of a set of information that can be used to develop customized products (Figure 2).

As illustrated in figure 2, the data extracted from the user are subject to the analysis and evaluation by a specialized technician with skills in interpreting human signals. Whether this information results from a transaction based process (as is the case of the pressure maps) or from a communication process based on a set of pragmatic information (for instance: facial expression, humor, or other factors external to the evaluation process), it lacks specialized interpretation from a process of communication/interaction of information.

A system named "Core System" was then developed. This system was programmed using LabView software for entering inputs into the system. The Core System was designed to integrate different contributions from a large amount of information collected. Through the use of communication tools, information is obtained regarding users, suppliers and manufacturers. This situation leads to a dynamic

Figure 2. Communication integrated process between user and technician.

integration system, where all process parts contribute with blocks of information.

CORE SYSTEM

Core System is an application developed based on user centered design methodologies, in this particular case focusing people with special needs that by physical impairments depend on wheelchairs as a means for locomotion or that due to lack of movement autonomy need to remain seated for long periods of time. The Core System is structured in small sequential modules, from which it interacts at various levels, ranging from data collection to data treatment and preparation for manufacture, using a system that is open to the introduction of new modules.

The Core System (figure 3), allows data integration from a network or database in any stage of the product life cycle, building a collaborative work between user, psychophysics' experts, suppliers/materials and producers/manufacturing

technologies, regardless of its geographical location or business area. Designed from three modules: acquisition system module; seat design module and manufacturing module, the system performs the integration between user data (tangible or intangible) with material data and the data that originates the seat base shape.

These modules process the information, from emotional/psychophysical data interpretation (based on mood scales, facial expressions, movement acquisition and pressure data) to the generation of a virtual three-dimensional surface that can be exported to a CAD system and that considers material behavior according to the expected final result.

Acquisition System Module

The first module (orange block in figure 3) is an acquisition module that represents the interaction with the psychophysical tools and users that generates two types of semiotic information with different

Figure 3. Integration System Framework.

characteristics. The left side of figure 3 shows a set of emotional/psychophysical data acquisition tools. The semantic informations are clear, objective and quantitative (such as the pressure map) and it is possible to measure and transfer them to the next module, while the more pragmatic informations are confuse, subjective and qualitative, and therefore need interpretation by the technician.

In the case of facial expression, Borg CR10 scale and MOCAP, a set of qualitatively measurable information is generated, where features as mood or environment can be determinant in the facial expression and questionnaire response. In the case of MOCAP, this essentially serves as a tool to support the selection of the moment, or moments, to consider during pressure evaluation so as to, by the crossing with pressure maps, identify which areas are being affected and which is the user's reflection to the stimulus. The clear identification of these areas is crucial to the process since these are the areas more propitious to the development of PUs. This is the reason why these data require a psychophysics technician to perform their semiotic interpretation in order to validate the data. The pressure maps, on the other hand, as mentioned above, allow quantitative information, thus objective information, thus measurable.

Figure 3 presents a set of curved lines that represent dynamic information. In the case of the first module they are connected to the user, allowing the generation of data information, based on the user, data that will be used and processed in the design module.

Figure 2 shows that in the acquisition module, the quantitative information, acquired by means of pressure maps is directly transferred to the core system through technical supervision, while in the case of Borg CR10 and MOCAP the process is based on interaction, since, resorting to communication between expert and user, the information is built based in this relationship, and therefore data such as their cognitive and emotional relationship interfere both in terms of building the information as in terms of information interpretation.

Finally it is important to notice that in this module the information generated is unique, exclusive, which results from each user having different values, that in turn result in a custom seat base unable to be used by other users, since the final shape may be uncomfortable to others.

Seat design module

The second module is the seat design module, represented in green in figure 3. The most significant

part of the work developed was focused in this module of the Core System. This module involves the information, collected from the user, as well as its treatment aiming at minimizing, as much as possible, the pressure exerted. This minimization is achieved through an improvement in the pressure distribution and by the conversion of this information into a three-dimensional design of a seat base shape that allows ensuring this relationship.

This module converts the pressure information from XYZ data into geometrical coordinates. Combining this geometry with informations regarding the features of the materials for production, obtained from suppliers and manufacturers, this module translates the result into a virtual 3D surface designed in CAD. The module also allows considering the dynamic information from manufacturers, regarding the manufacturing process, in order to adjust or redesign the 3D shape accordingly.

The 3D seat base generated by the seat design module, due to its profile permits transferring the pressure forces from the contact zones, more conducive to the emergence of PUs, to areas with greater muscular mass. Thus the seat base created allows a better relation in pressure forces distribution, reducing the risk of PU development.

Manufacturing Module

The third and final module is the manufacturing module, pointed out in blue in figure 3. This module is based upon the data from the seat design module combined with prime materials suppliers as well as with manufacturers. This manufacturing module allows processing the information from the CAD system into machine code generation according to the manufacturing process.

Given the new approaches of the global economy, based on relocation and in working methodologies established in global networks, the manufacturing and in particular the production of small series of customized products became embroiled in a logic where suppliers and industry are part of central information systems allowing an information management in real time. In the present case, this information management is present in the integration

of data from materials and suppliers in the seat design module, and considering the alternative production systems when creating the machine code according to the production processes and offers from the most economically viable industries in the manufacturing module.

The group of curved lines at the right side of figure 3, represent the dynamic information associated with the suppliers of production prime materials. This dynamic feature is dependent of the market offer, offer that can imply different production/manufacturing process and consequently changes in the generation of machine code.

In the present work a seat base was obtained with the desired characteristics, this seat base allowed a better pressure force distribution that was manifested in the increase of the time of tolerance, and consequent decrease of the need to reposition the user, that passed from 2 to 8 hours.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study addresses the emotional relations with the user, based in an integrated user centered design perspective, using as a particular case study people with special needs, that due to their disabilities spend great part of their time seated. This type of patient ends up suffering from pressure ulcers, having this been the reason for using this particular user as reference for the study of a user based methodology.

From the developed model a set of integrated modules has resulted, the first of which refers to the collection of informations based on the user and that, from the validation of emotional and psychophysical data, allows retrieving the necessary information for the development of a virtual seat base, by the second module, capable of minimizing the possibility of pressure ulcers occurrence. This virtual seat base is designed based on a better distribution of the pressure areas, achieved by data treatment in this module. The third and final module transforms the virtual seat base into a real product that allowed to increase the time of tolerance, passing from 2 to 8 hours for the same pressure values, values which are conducive to pressure ulcer occurrence, and

consequently increasing user comfort noticeable in the emotional relationship with the object.

The semiotic values, after the information treatment, were integrated in acquisition system module, the first of the Core System, being part of an integrated system that emerges as an alternative tool for the creation of customized products that meet users needs.

The current system represents a group of subsystems that integrate all parts of the process, precisely because the approach used for its development was based on a method of communication process. That means that although we have an integrated system, it is possible to modify the inputs in each module and those modifications are reflected on the final result.

Thus, this work presents itself as a system which comprises the various aspects of the emotional design, given that the result allows in one hand assessing physiological comfort characteristics, and in the other hand, from the interpretation in the communication process, allows understanding the cognitive relationship that the user has with the object, influencing the selection of materials characteristics to consider for new products development, either in terms of rigidity as in terms of the surface treatment.

A contemporaneous vision of the manufacturing industries, based on production by rapid prototyping and the integration of industries based in the internet, permitted that the model, being itself integrator, can also consider references of materials and manufacturing techniques as well as industries location, to thereby generate a more suitable response to the user that is reflected in a greater user satisfaction.

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